

Equilibrium, Non-equilibrium and Acoustic Properties of Liquids

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The present review gives a brief introduction to liquid state theories and gives the latest applications of the theory of liquids to alloys, fused salts, polymers and the derivative of potential function operating in liquids. The application of these potential function to obtain phonon frequencies and thermodynamic properties in commercially important liquids like Ge and Te has been described. We also give a novel method of evaluation of the diffusion coefficient and its pressure derivative.

Chemists and Liquids are inseparable. Thus many solvents used are liquids and many reactions are conducted in solutions. Thus a systematic molecular study of liquids will lead to a greater understanding of the forces operating in liquid state and hence the utilisation of these results to practical use.

The most fundamental property in liquid is the structure factor (SF). X-Ray crystallographers call it as interference function and is denoted by $S(k)$. Thus $S(k)$ is a function of momentum vector k . The Fourier transform (FT) of the SF is the well known radial distribution function (RDF) and is given by

$$g(r) = 1 + \frac{1}{2\pi^2 \rho r} \int k [S(k) - 1] \sin kr dk \quad (1)$$

The RDF is connected to several thermodynamic functions, such as the nearest neighbour distance, the first coordination number, the compressibility, the Helmholtz free energy and so on. Hence we will first describe some aspects of the theoretical methods of evaluating these fundamental properties, namely the SF or RDF.

The first attempt to theoretically evaluate the RDF is due to Born, Yvon and Green^{1,2}. But this equation can be solved only through the so called superposition approximation due to Kirkwood³ and does not give good results and is applicable only at very low number densities and hence not useful

to liquids. The real breakthrough is achieved when closed equations were formulated by Percus and Yevick⁴ and through the introduction of hypernetted chain equations^{5,6}. The Percus-Yevick equation is

$$g(r_{12}) \beta u(r_{12}) = 1 + \rho \int f(r_{13}) y(r_{13}) h(r_{23}) dr_3 \quad (2)$$

Here $g(r_{12})$ is the RDF and r_{12} is the distance between particles 1 and 2, $u(r_{12})$ the potential energy of interaction between particles 1 and 2, $f(r_{13})$ is the Mayer function and is given by

$$f(r) = e^{-\beta u(r)} - 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{while } y(r) = g(r) e^{\beta u(r)} \quad (4)$$

$$h(r) = g(r) - 1 = \text{Total correlation function} \quad (5)$$

Here $dr_3 = dx_3 dy_3 dz_3$ is the volume element in which any third particle is enclosed and ρ is the number density.

The HNC equation is given by

$$\ln y(r_{12}) = \rho \int [h(r_{13}) - \ln g(r_{13}) - u(r_{13})/kT] \times [g(r_{23}) - 1] dr_3 \quad (6)$$

Another very important correlation function that is most needed in Statistical Mechanical calculations is the direct correlation function (DCF) defined by Ornstein-Zernike⁷ and is given by

$$h(r_{12}) = c(r_{12}) + \rho \int c(r_{13}) h(r_{23}) dr_3 \quad (7)$$

Here $c(r_{12})$ is the direct correlation function (DCF) between particles 1 and 2, while the integral gives the contribution to the total correlation function $h(r)$ by any third particle.

From equations (2) and (7) it is possible to obtain an analytical expression for the direct correlation function for a hard sphere potential. Such an expression was obtained by Wertheim⁸ and Thiele⁹. The expression they obtained for hard sphere potential is given by

$$c(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\lambda_1 + \frac{6\lambda_2\eta r}{\sigma} + \frac{\eta\lambda_1 r^3}{2\sigma^3} \right] & r \leq \sigma \\ 0 & r > \sigma \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here σ is the hard sphere diameter and

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{(1+2\eta)^2}{(1-\eta)^4} \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \frac{(1+\eta/2)^2}{(1-\eta)^4}$$

while $\eta = \pi\rho\sigma^3/6$

The Fourier transform (FT) of the DCF is related to the SF of monatomic liquids by the following relation,

$$S(k) = [1 - \rho c(k)]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

where $c(k)$ is the FT of $c(r)$.

Application to metals :

The hard sphere $c(r)$ which is purely due to repulsive interaction can be coupled with any attractive part of the potential through the Mean Spherical Model Approximation¹⁰. Thus the total $c(r)$ including the attractive part is given by

$$c(r) = \begin{cases} c_{hs}(r) & r \leq \sigma \\ -\beta u_{Att}(r) & r > \sigma \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $c_{hs}(r)$ is the DCF due to hard spheres and $u_{Att}(r)$ is the attractive part of the potential and $\beta = 1/k_B T$. Here k_B is the Boltzmann's constant. Rao and coworkers evaluated the structure factor of several metals and non-metals using square-well attractive tail as a perturbation over hard spheres¹¹⁻¹⁵.

We give in Fig. 1 the structure factors of Pt and Pd obtained in this way.

Fig. 1

Application to alloys :

These calculations can also be extended to alloys as well through the use of Lebowitz-Baxter solution^{16,17} for $C_{ij}(r)$ for hard sphere mixtures with an attractive square-well tail. The various equations have been copiously described by the authors in several papers¹⁸⁻²¹ on alloys. We give in Figs. 2 and 3 the computed total structure factor of Hg-In and Mg-Zn alloys along with the experimental values.

Another important aspect of the application of Lebowitz solution of hard sphere mixtures¹⁶ is in the case of certain metals which show a strong right-hand shoulder in their structure factor. The structure factor of these metals can be explained by assuming two types of diameters in the melt. In the solid state they do exhibit several polymorphic forms and these forms persist near the melting point. We given in Fig. 4A the structure factors of Sb and Bi²². It appears that elements like Bi and Sb can be treated as simple hard sphere mixtures while in the case of metals like Ga and Sn, a square-well attractive tail is used as a perturbation

Fig. 2

over the hard sphere mixture²². The calculated structure factors of these two metals along with experimental values are shown in Fig. 4B.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4A

Fig. 4B

Applications to fused salts :

Waisman and Lebowitz²³ obtained an expression for the partial direct correlation function $C_{ij}(r)$ of ions having equal diameters. A very general solution for $C_{ij}(r)$ of ions of any size has been obtained by Blum²⁴ and these equations have been recasted into a useful computational form by Hiroike²⁵.

After examining the various forms of $C_{ij}(r)$ Rao and Pal²⁶ and Rao and Das Gupta²⁷ postulated that even for charged hard spheres like Na^+ or Cl^- ions which have unequal diameters the form of $C_{ij}(r)$ remains the same inside the core of ions. According to Rao and Pal²⁶ the $C_{ij}(r)$ can be written as

$$C_{ij}^{\text{WL}}(r) = [C_{\text{hs}}(r)]_{ij}^{\text{WT}} - \frac{\beta_{ij} Q_{ij}}{\epsilon \sigma_{ij}} \left[2 B_{ij} - \frac{r B_{ij}^2}{\sigma_{ij}} \right] \quad r \leq \sigma_{ij} \quad (12a)$$

$$C_{ij}(r) = \frac{q_i q_j}{\epsilon k_B T} \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) \quad r > \sigma_{ij} \quad (12b)$$

$$B_{ij} = \frac{1}{\zeta_{ij}} \left[1 + \zeta_{ij} - (1 + 2 \zeta_{ij})^{1/2} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\zeta_{ij} = k_D \sigma_{ij} \quad (14)$$

$$k_D = \frac{4 \pi}{k_B T \epsilon} \sum \rho_i Q_i^2 \quad (15)$$

Here $C_{ij}(r)$ is the DCF between the ions i and j and $[C_{\text{hs}}(r)]_{ij}^{\text{WT}}$ is the Wertheim-Thiele DCF. From these expressions with a proper choice of the diameter σ_{ij} of the ion one can obtain the Fourier Transform of $C_{ij}(r)$ and using Rushbrook-Pearson's equations²⁸ one can obtain the partial structure factors of the ions from $C^{-ij}(k)$.

The most generalised solution for the DCF of unequal diameters for charged hard spheres as given by Blum²⁴ and recasted by Hiroike²⁵ has been applied to RbCl and RbBr ²⁹ and to 50% AuCs alloy which behaves like a salt³⁰. The partial RDF of RbCl as calculated through Blums equations are shown in Fig. 5.

In two important papers, Rao and Venkatesh^{31,32} described in detail a method of evaluating the heats of vapourisation of fused salts. Starting with neutral hard spheres the entropy of vapourisation is calculated. The entropy contribution in overcoming the attraction is computed through the use of a potential function. In these calculations we use the principle that the total entropy is a sum of the contributions from hard spheres and coulomb interactions³³. The calculated results are given in Table 1.

Fig. 5

Table 1

Salt	Temp. °C	V cm ³	ΔS_{Th}	ΔS_{Expt}	$\Delta S_{\text{Th}}/\Delta S_{\text{Expt}}$
NaCl	808	37.65	163.4	175.1	0.93
KCl	772	48.84	171.0	174.7	0.98
CsCl	645	60.31	193.5	185.2	1.04
NaBr	747	43.94	171.0	174.4	0.98
KBr	734	55.95	178.5	173.1	1.03
CsBr	636	68.0	184.3	176.0	1.05
KI	685	68.0	178.1	174.0	1.02

Statistical mechanics of polymers :

The experimental results obtained by small angle neutron, X-ray diffraction and light scattering results can be very well explained with liquid state statistical mechanical equations and one can obtain several important properties of polymer dispersions and emulsions. Thus we can get the coordination number, the nearest neighbour distance, the interplanar distance, the diffusion coefficient, compressibility and reduced intensities³⁴⁻³⁶ etc.

Derivation of potential from experimental structure factor :

An important aspect of the study of structure factors is the evaluation of potential function from the experimentally measured structure factors. Rao and Joardar³⁷ derived a relation between structure

factor and potential function which is given by

$$\beta\phi(r) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2\rho} \int_r^\infty \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \int_0^\infty \left[\frac{S(k) - 1}{S(k)} \right] [k\alpha \cos k\alpha - \sin k\alpha] dk d\alpha \quad (16)$$

$$1 + \frac{1}{2\pi^2\rho\alpha} \int_0^\infty [S(k) - 1] k \sin k\alpha dk$$

This equation has been applied to several metals³⁸ and polymers³⁶. We show in Figs. 6 and 7 the

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

potential functions of liquid Ge³⁸ and Te³⁹ respectively while in Fig. 8 we give that of polymerised silica³⁶.

Fig. 8

Radial distribution function, and dynamic properties :

The application of non-equilibrium statistical mechanics to obtain numerical results is fast progressing. The evaluation of velocity autocorrelation function is one such property. Pioneering calculations have been made by Rahman⁴⁰ who obtained a negative region in the velocity autocorrelation function (VACF). This negative region in the autocorrelation function is due to back-scattering of the atoms by the short ranged core collisions⁴¹.

The VACF of liquid Cu⁴² and Ag⁴² are shown in Figs. 9A and 9B respectively. The function shows a rapid initial decay and goes through a negative region and finally approaches zero in an oscillation manner. The VACF can be used to compute the diffusion coefficient of the particles in the liquid and the power spectrum of the liquid. The latter is useful in calculating the characteristic frequency with which the particles oscillate⁴².

A simple theory which depicts the Brownian motion of the particles diffusing in harmonic well with a characteristic frequency ω_0 can be written as⁴³

Fig. 9A

$$\frac{d^2 \psi(t)}{dt^2} + \beta_0 \frac{d\psi(t)}{dt} + \omega_0^2 \psi(t) = 0 \quad (17)$$

Here $\psi(t)$ is the normalised VACF defined by

$$\psi(t) = \frac{\langle V(t) V(0) \rangle}{\langle V^2 \rangle} \quad (18)$$

and β_0 is a constant related to the diffusion coefficient. Equation (17) is solved through a set of boundary conditions⁴⁴. Further, the characteristic frequency ω_0 is related to the potential function as

$$\frac{\langle \nabla^2 \phi \rangle}{3M} = \omega_0 = \frac{4\pi\rho}{3M} \int dr r^2 g(r) \left[\phi''(r) + \frac{2\phi'(r)}{r} \right] \quad (19)$$

Thus one can obtain the derivatives of the potential function from equation (16)³⁸. However one can also use a model potential function and obtain the potential energy derivatives. Thus for liquid Ge³⁸ and Te³⁹ the potential energy derivatives are obtained from equation (16), while for a transition metal like Cr⁴⁵ we use the model potential as formulated by Bretonnett and Deroache⁴⁶ and Wills and Harrison⁴⁷ and obtain the derivatives⁴⁷.

These derivatives can be used to obtain the phonon frequencies in liquids using various equations derived by different authors⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. The phonon fre-

Fig. 9B

quencies calculated through Bhatia-Singh's equations⁵⁰ and through Hubbard and Beeby's equations⁴⁹ for liquid Ge³⁸ and Te³⁹ are shown in Figs. 10

Fig. 10

and 11 respectively. The various equations used are involved and those interested may see the original papers.

The third derivative of the potential function can be obtained from the second and it is shown⁵¹ that the Grüneisen's constant γ_G is related to the third and second derivatives of the potential energy as

$$\gamma_G = -\frac{1}{6} r_0 \frac{\phi'''(r)}{\phi''(r)} \Big|_{r=r_0} \quad (20)$$

Fig. 11

Here r_0 is the nearest neighbour distance and can be obtained from the position of the first peak of the RDF. Thus the Grüneisen's constant calculated for liquid Ge³⁸ and Te³⁹ is 1.39 and 2.13 respectively.

The calculations of phonon frequencies to alloys form an extension of the method already described for metals. Such calculations have been made for several alloys^{52,53}. Mention may be made that the structure factors can be profitably used in the evaluation of transport properties like diffusion coefficient^{54,55}, electrical conductivity⁵⁶ etc. It is very difficult to include the application of structure factors or RDF in the computation of transport properties in one review.

Elastic constants of high frequency moduli and RDF :

From the phonon frequency distribution it is possible to compute the elastic constants from the low frequency values. They can also be calculated from Schofield's equations⁵⁷. Using the number of nearest neighbours and from the first and second derivatives of the potential function at r_0 , the nearest neighbour distance, one can obtain the elastic constants through Bhatia-Singh's equation⁵⁰. Such calculations have been made for liquid Ge³⁸ and Te³⁹ and NiB melts⁵⁸. We give in Table 2 the elastic constants of liquid Ge.

TABLE 2— ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF LIQUID GERMANIUM

Method	C_{11} in units of 10^{11}	C_{44} $N\ m^{-2}$
From β and δ	0.55	0.042
From phonon frequencies (Bhatia-Singh's Method)	0.51	0.040
From velocity of sound	0.53	0.04

We conclude this review by describing a novel method of calculating the diffusion coefficient and its pressure derivative⁵⁹. Kirkwood and Rice⁶⁰ in an important paper derived an expression for the friction constant and from the statistical mechanical definition of characteristic frequency (vide equation 19) it is possible to show that the diffusion coefficient is given by⁵⁹

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{M \omega_D} \quad (21)$$

One can calculate ω_D the Debye frequency from specific heats and obtain the diffusion coefficient from the above equation. The calculated values for some typical metals and non-metals are given in Table 3. Further it is shown that the pressure derivative of the diffusion coefficient is given by⁵⁹

$$\left[\frac{\partial \ln D}{\partial P} \right] = -\gamma_G \beta_T \quad (22)$$

Here β_T is the isothermal compressibility. The calculated values for some typical substances are given

TABLE 3 – DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT (D) FOR SOME TYPICAL SUBSTANCES

Substance	K	D ($10^{-5}\ cm^2\ s^{-1}$)	
		Calcd.	Expt.
K	335.5	3.62	3.71
Cu	1356.0	4.11	3.99
Te	723.0	2.63	2.50
Pb	601.0	2.1	2.2
In	430.0	1.63	1.68
Ar	86.0	1.62	1.60
CCl ₄	300.0	1.37	1.20
C ₆ H ₆	293.0	1.94	1.91
CH ₄	112.0	3.3	3.7

in Table 4 along with experiment wherever available.

TABLE 4

Substance	From equation (22) in units of 10^{-11}	Expt. cm^2/dyne	Swalins values
Hg	1.10	1.0	1.0
K	5.10	5.6	5.4
Rb	6.2	4.5	5.0
CCl ₄	9.5	—	9.7
CS ₂	9.74	—	8.4
C ₆ H ₆	8.10	—	8.4

Thus we conclude this review by pointing out that the structure factor and its Fourier transform namely the RDF can be used to compute several properties of liquids and amorphous solids and hence their probable use.

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